

Assessing the Role of Forestation in maintaining ecological integrity in Bangladesh

Md. Mizanur Rahman

Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh

E-mail: rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

The overarching objective of the study was to assess the role of forestation in maintaining ecological integrity in Bangladesh. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. It was found that environmental degradation can be improved through plantation and forestation. Afforestation can combat the adverse effect of climate change and improve the existing microclimatic pattern. The forestation can act as a greenbelt against tropical cyclones in the coastal areas. The depleted biodiversity can be enriched by controlling incremental biological Invasion. It can ease riparian habitat complexity and improve soil qualities. The study recommended integrated forest management emphasizing riparian plantation, fallow land plantation, gap filling, natural succession, natural regeneration and community-based coastal forestation.

Keywords: Ecological integrity, biological invasion, greenbelt, habitat complexity, community-based plantation

Introduction

Forest ecosystem provides benefits that support the livelihoods of countless human beings (Pastur *et al.* 2018; Corvalan *et al.* 2005, Weiskopf *et al.* 2020). Forests provide many components to the broad range of ecological services such as regulation of rainfall and hydrological system; maintenance of soil quality, control of soil erosion, modulation of climate; and being the habitat of biodiversity (Balloffet *et al.* 2012; Thompson *et al.* 2009; Schoenholtz *et al.* 2000). Forests form the basis of different industries e.g., timber, wood processing, paper, rubber, paints, resin, gum, honey, food, medicines, building material, fodder, game, tourism, etc. (Korhonen *et al.* 2001; Ahammad *et al.* 2021; Hoque *et al.* 2018; Rahman & Vacik 2010; Rahman *et al.* 2010). Forests are home to millions of people all around the world and they are dependent on the forests for their survival (FAO 2020; Rahman 2021, Rahman 2022a, b).

Every nation has strong cultural and spiritual attachments to forests. Aesthetics and beauty are important components of forest services (Laband, 2013). These services are connected and sustained through the integrity of the ecosystems. It is quite impossible to compare the importance of the various services provided by forests as there is no universally accepted common metric that can be used in such measurement.

The natural Forest in Bangladesh is threatened and highly degraded (Rahman 2009; Rahman 2023a, b; Rahman *et al.* 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010). Until the beginning of the 20th century, these forests existed as a continuous belt with rich floral and faunal diversity. Gradually increasing population put tremendous pressure on the forest and changed the scenario (Rahman *et al.* 2007, Rahman and Vacik 2010b, Rahman 2021, 2022a, b; Rahman and Vacik 2009, 2010b). These forests at present are under occupation and the remaining stands are of poor stocking. The massive destruction of the forests of Bangladesh occurred during the last 40 years. Biodiversity has declined rapidly and many species have disappeared. The forests are acutely impacted by over-exploitation, deforestation, excessive litter collection, encroachment, indiscriminate collection of economically important plant species (i.e., medicinal, fodder etc.), and other forms of anthropogenic disturbances. Hence, the study aimed to assess the role of forestation in maintaining ecological integrity in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different sources of literature. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to understand the role of forestation in improving ecological integrity. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

The Role of Forestation in Bangladesh

Combating global warming

The respondents opined that climate change and forests are interlinked. The increased destruction of forests is recognized as one of the main causes of climate change. Forests can trap and store carbon dioxide, playing a major role in mitigating climate change. On the flip side of the coin, forests become the sources of the greenhouse gas, carbon dioxide when destroyed or over-harvested and burned. Forests, if not harmed ensure that they are enabled to continue to produce the benefits; to mitigate the effects of a changing climate; to compensate for fossil fuel emissions through carbon storage; and to enhance ecosystem health, sustainability, and resilience. Forests reduce greenhouse gas emissions to combat global warming. Greenhouse gas emissions result from deforestation and the degradation of forests. Fossil fuels release carbon dioxide into the atmosphere contributing to global warming and climate change. Forest alleviates this change by converting carbon dioxide to carbon during photosynthesis. This carbon is stored in the form of wood and vegetation through "carbon sequestration". The forest acts as a "carbon sink" by storing carbon.

Enriching Biodiversity

The forest will improve the degraded food chains. The degraded forests will be converted into successional forests. Due to massive deforestation, most of the species of wildlife have become threatened and rare. Rapid deforestation leads to the extinction of hundreds of plants and dozens of birds and animal species. The forestation can improve the scenarios and restore the periled biodiversity of Bangladesh.

Easing riparian habitat complexity

Water temperature regulates the physiology and ecology of different like littoral and lentic biota. It influences the distribution, behaviour and survival of biota. Riparian forestation can decrease water temperature, thermocline deepening, habitat complexity and insulation, and increase littoral shading. This forestation also will decrease the down-slope salinity and nitrate contamination in surface runoff. Riparian forestation can increase wildlife refuges, especially for amphibians and reptiles (Rahman 2023 c, d).

Changing in micro-climatic pattern

The plant absorbs water from the soil through roots and releases it into the atmosphere during transpiration. This released water then forms clouds and rains. Forestation can heal the environmental damage in Bangladesh. Forestation in Bangladesh can change the extreme climatic pattern.

Improving soil properties

Deforestation exposes the forest soil to the sun, making it very dry and eventually, infertile, due to volatile nutrients such as nitrogen being lost. The rainfall washes away the rest of the nutrients, which flow with the rainwater into waterways. The soil stands devoid of essential nutrients. Large tracts of land are rendered permanently impoverished due to soil erosion. Deforestation causes drought and desertification. Deforestation disrupts the regulation of the flow of water. It also increases salinity in the soil. It alters the microclimate of a place thus affecting the habitats of endemic species. Tree roots bind the underlying bedrock. Deforestation increases the risk of landslides. Forestation in Bangladesh can combat these challenges.

Controlling biological Invasion

Both climate change and invasive species are highly correlated. They are the extraordinary ecological challenges to Bangladesh today (Rahman 2020, 2023e). Climate change alters destination habitats and increases vulnerability to invasion because of resource scarcity and increased competition among native fauna and flora. Changes in precipitation, nitrogen deposition and temperature will have a tremendous impact on the geographic ranges of many species. Increased temperature will allow the spread northward of some species currently restricted in their northern ranges. Stressed ecosystems facilitate the successful invasion of non-native plants. Forestation in Bangladesh can halt the supremacy of invasive species.

Greenbelt against the tropical cyclones

Deforestation exacerbates cyclonic impacts. Forests act as a buffer between the cyclone and the habitat area. The impacts of the cyclone *Aila*, *Sidr* and *Nargis* were devastating due to the deforestation of the Sundarbans mangroves. The destructions were so severe due to deforestation. Bangladesh will be more vulnerable to increased cyclones if deforestation is not stopped and forestation is started. The massive deforestation of the Sundarbans will expose the entire southern part of Bangladesh to frequent cyclones.

Integrated forest management

- * Devising the basic requirements for near-natural silviculture
- * Monitoring the impact of climate change on forests and devising appropriate strategies
- * Dealing with biotic damage in forests like infestation of wood-boring beetles and forest fires
- * Coordinating national and international forest policy
- * Improving land use patterns and protecting forest lands
- * Involving indigenous peoples and traditional communities in the conservation programme
- * Introducing afforestation and reforestation by introducing pioneer and early successional species
- * Facilitating natural regeneration in degraded forests
- * Leaving denuded forest lands untouched for 20 years to promote natural succession
- * Stopping further clear felling and illegal logging
- * Protecting natural regenerations (seedling, sapling and juvenile trees) from cutting
- * Taking effective actions against encroachers and land grabbers
- * Increasing basic research on the impact of forest degradation

- * Alleviating poverty in the adjacent areas of forests
- * Emphasizing community-based conservation
- * Establishing more protected areas
- * Searching for alternative fuel sources in the forest and adjacent areas
- * Taking care of secondary and successional forests
- * Declaring riparian vegetation as the refuge ecosystem for plant and wildlife
- * Prohibiting clearance of wood and shrubs within 25 m on both sides of any waterway
- * Preserving not only the riverfront, interior and riparian forest edge but also parts of the adjacent upland forest
- * Undertaking afforestation on the open dunes by the plant species which have 'prop roots to anchor themselves in the loose sand
- * Maintaining at least two canopy layers (bimodal or reverse J-shaped diameter distribution)
- * Maintaining at least two main canopy tree species suited to the sites
- * Undertaking passive management to develop tree-size canopy structures and decadence
- * Planting large-diameter trees with strong root systems to provide critical structure
- * Designing and establishing a sea-level/climate modelling network
- * Integrating coastal and marine management
- * Conducting coastal vulnerability and risk assessment
- * Initiating community-based coastal forestation
- * Introducing afforestation and reforestation by salt-tolerant species

- * Introducing desirable trees to shade out the regeneration of invasive species
- * Digging out and burning the thickets of the invasive species
- * Using microbial and other biological agents to control invasion

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